

Automated Thermal Imaging for Diabetic Foot Risk Assessment

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Abstract— Diabetic foot is a prevalent complication affecting approximately 25% of individuals with diabetes, often leading to ulcers and amputations. Thermography is established as a non-invasive technique for early detection and monitoring of such complications by analyzing plantar temperature distribution and asymmetry. However, current software solutions are either dependent on specific camera systems or lack transparency and accessibility, limiting their clinical applicability. This study presents the development and validation of an automated tool for segmenting anatomical regions of interest (ROIs) in thermal foot images to support early diagnosis and monitoring of diabetic foot complications. The proposed system uses an object detection model trained on 92 annotated thermal images from two camera models. The algorithm identifies foot regions, applies edge detection and temperature-based thresholding, and extracts five ROIs per foot, using geometrical and temperature cues to define anatomical boundaries. The model was integrated as an API into the Vizbox Thermal Analysis platform, enabling interactive visualization and refinement of the segmented ROIs. Evaluation using the Dice Similarity Coefficient showed high agreement with manual annotations across all ROIs (Dice > 0.75), with minimal segmentation failures. The tool also reduced the time and effort required for manual adjustments. The proposed solution offers a robust and efficient method for anatomical segmentation of thermal foot images. Its performance and integration into an existing platform demonstrate its potential as a practical support tool for diabetic foot screening and monitoring.

Keywords— image processing, image segmentation, computer vision, thermography, diabetic foot.

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a chronic endocrine disease characterized by persistent hyperglycemia due to alterations in the secretion or action of insulin [1]–[3]. Its prevalence in Brazil is approximately 9% [4], [5]. Its main complications include vascular, neuropathic, cardiac, renal, hepatic, and ocular complications [1], [6], [7].

Diabetic neuropathy is one of the most frequent complications in people with diabetes, with estimates

exceeding 50% of diabetes cases [8]–[11]. This condition compromises sensitivity in the feet, making it difficult to perceive trauma and increasing the risk of injury [7], [12].

In addition, impaired circulation, which is common in people with diabetes, impairs the healing of injuries [1], [7], [12], [13]. As a result, these injuries can develop into ulcers, leading to lower limb amputation and even death [14]–[19].

Thus, an important complication is known as diabetic foot that has a high prevalence among diabetic individuals, around 25% [20], [21]. Amongst these, it is estimated that the recurrence of foot ulcers is 40% after the first year, and 60% after three years [13], [20], [22].

To aid in this diagnosis and monitoring of lesions, thermography has been consolidated as a promising non-invasive technique for screening and early diagnosis of foot complications in diabetic patients [18], [23]. Studies have shown that monitoring plantar temperature allows pre-ulcerative inflammation spots to be identified, with evidence indicating that a thermal difference ≥ 2.2 °C between corresponding regions of the feet is associated with a greater risk of ulceration [6], [11], [16], [20].

In addition, asymmetrical patterns of thermal distribution, such as the loss of the so-called “butterfly pattern” typical of healthy individuals, have been observed in diabetic patients [13], [18], [20], [24].

Although many studies focus on increased temperature as a sign of inflammation, the presence of cold regions also represents an important risk factor: these areas may indicate insufficient blood perfusion resulting from microvascular dysfunction [6], [19], [25].

This way, thermography can also contribute to the screening of patients at risk of ulceration associated with vascular dysfunction [26]–[28].

In this context, this study aims to develop software for the automatic segmentation of ROIs of the foot in thermal images, to support early diagnosis and monitoring of diabetic foot.

A. Justification

Despite advances in scientific evidence supporting the use of thermography for the screening and monitoring of diabetic foot complications, its practical application still faces challenges [16], [23], [25], [29], [30]. The most common evaluation method involves the use of generic thermal visualization softwares, such as those provided by camera manufacturers themselves, which allows professionals to inspect images, apply color scales, and measure temperatures at specific points. This approach enables visual interpretation and analysis based on thermal asymmetry and heat distribution patterns [1], [20], [22], [25]. However, this method relies heavily on the examiner's experience for both marking and interpreting the results.

Currently, there are specialized software tools designed for thermal analysis of the lower limbs, but their commercial availability is limited, being available only bundled with specific cameras distributed by the software developers [31], [32]. Moreover, in many cases, detailed information on the methods used specifically for diabetic foot analysis is not accessible, which limits the evaluation of their clinical applicability [31], [32].

In the academic domain, two main approaches stand out: the creation of ROIs based on foot anatomy in thermal images for the analysis of distribution and asymmetry [16], [29], [33], [34], and the classification of ulceration risk using artificial intelligence algorithms [7], [11], [12], [20], [29], [35].

Given the lack of accessible solutions, this study proposes the development of a tool that integrates standardized thermal segmentation with both individual and comparative analysis of anatomical foot regions, while maintaining compatibility with different camera models and manufacturers. This approach is expected to support early detection of ulcerative lesions and aid clinical decision-making.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

For training the AI model and performing development tests, 92 thermal images, divided into two sets, were used. The first set contains 48 thermal images captured with a Fluke Ti400 camera, with a resolution of 320×240 pixels, a temperature range of -20 °C to 80 °C, and a sensitivity of 0.05 °C. The second set includes 44 thermal images acquired with a Flir T530 camera, with a resolution of 320×240 pixels, a temperature range of -20 °C to 120 °C, and a sensitivity of 0.04 °C.

Manual annotation was performed to identify and locate each foot region in the dataset used to train the object detection model. The online tool CVAT was used for this

purpose, allowing the creation of bounding boxes associated with the target class. All 92 images were annotated with a single class, and the annotations were exported in YOLO 1.1 format.

The model was trained using the YOLOv8 architecture through the Ultralytics library in a local environment. The training was executed for 500 epochs, with a batch size of 16 images and an input resolution of 320×320 pixels. Horizontal flipping was applied as a data augmentation technique. The dataset was split in a 90% to 10% ratio for training and validation, respectively.

The algorithm takes as input a CSV file containing the temperature matrix of the thermal image. From this matrix, a grayscale image is generated, with values normalized between 19 °C and 34 °C.

The resulting image is then processed by the previously described object detection model. As output, the model returns a list of n detections, each represented by a bounding box and its corresponding confidence score.

To determine the best match for each foot, two procedures are applied. First, redundant detections are eliminated by analyzing overlaps: pairs of bounding boxes in which the center of one lies within the area of another are compared, and the one with the lower confidence score is discarded (Fig. 1). Second, from the remaining detections, the two with the highest confidence scores are selected and assigned to the corresponding foot based on the horizontal position of their bounding boxes.

Fig. 1 Result of the detection box refinement process. Green rectangles indicate valid detections, red rectangles represent rejected detections, and yellow areas show removed regions.

After identifying the foot regions, the algorithm applies the Canny edge detection technique, resulting in a binary image that maps the edge pixels. Based on this image, the detection bounding boxes are refined by scanning along the four sides (top, bottom, left, and right) and identifying the first internal line that contains an edge pixel. This process allows the bounding boxes to be adjusted so they align more accurately with the actual foot contours.

From the area enclosed by each bounding box, five ROIs were defined. Initially, the foot was divided longitudinally into three sections: posterior, middle, and anterior. The posterior portion, corresponding to the heel region, was represented by a circular ROI. The middle and anterior portions were each subdivided into internal and external halves along the longitudinal axis of the foot, resulting in four additional ROIs represented as polygons. In total, five ROIs were defined in the model.

The identification of the first ROI, corresponding to the heel, begins with the selection of two points along the lower edge of the foot (Fig. 2). These points are obtained by scanning upward from the base of the detection bounding box over the Canny edge image. For each line, the first and last edge pixels are selected. If no such points are found or if they are too close, the search continues on the next line above.

Fig. 2 Representation of the two test points per foot. Small circles indicate their neighborhoods, and lines point toward the density center, with emphasis on the intersection point and the fitted heel circle.

For each of the two selected points, the local temperature density center is calculated within a circular neighborhood, allowing the algorithm to determine the direction in which the surrounding region is warmer relative to the center. The heel center is defined as the intersection point of the lines connecting each initial point to the center of mass of its respective neighborhood. The heel radius (HR) is estimated as the average distance between the test points and the calculated heel center.

Using the lowest temperature between the two test points selected during heel center estimation as the threshold, two binary images were generated, one for processing each foot.

The resulting images highlight regions with temperatures above the threshold, segmenting the foot area from the background. From these binary images, the additional points required for positioning the ROIs were extracted.

The points identified and used for constructing the polygons were labeled with a letter and a number. The letter indicates the transverse position of each point: “E” for the external margin, “I” for the internal margin and “C” for

points positioned on the longitudinal axis. The number specifies the position along the longitudinal axis: 1 for the anterior extremity of the foot, 2 for the division between the anterior and middle portions and 3 for the division between the middle portion and the heel.

Point C2, located at the boundary between the anterior and middle portions, is used along with the heel center to define the longitudinal axis of the foot. To identify it, an initial reference is set at the center of the bounding box in the X-axis and 40% from the top in the Y-axis. From this point, horizontal scans are performed to the left and right sides using the previously generated binary image to locate the lateral limits of the foot. The midpoint between these two limits is then assigned as C2 (Fig. 3).

Based on this point and the previously defined heel center, the angle representing the inclination of the foot is calculated. Subsequently, two new scans are performed perpendicular to the calculated foot inclination. The resulting limits are assigned to points E2 and I2.

Fig. 3 On the left, the initial point is shown in purple and the obtained point C2 in green. On the right, points E2 and I2 are highlighted in green, with the perpendicular line used to locate them and the longitudinal axis drawn in blue.

From C2, a line is drawn toward the anterior end of the foot, following the foot inclination. The last high-temperature pixel found in the binary image along this path is assumed to correspond approximately to the middle toe and is designated as point C1.

Next, a line is drawn between points C1 and E2. Starting at the midpoint of this line and perpendicular to it, a scan is started until the edge of the binary image is reached (Fig. 4). The endpoint of this scan corresponds to the smallest toe and is labeled as E1.

Fig. 4 Points C1 and E2 used as reference are indicated in purple, the obtained point E1 is highlighted in green, and the lines used in the process are drawn in blue.

To locate point I1, corresponding to the hallux, a search region was defined between the center of the foot and the upper inner corner of the detection bounding box (Fig. 5). Within this region, positive pixels from the Canny edge image were evaluated. The distance between each of the pixels and the foot center was calculated. The most distant pixel was then designated as I1.

Fig. 5 Image resulting from the application of the Canny filter. The foot detection box is indicated in faded blue, the region used for the distance test is highlighted in blue, the reference point is in purple, and the farthest point, corresponding to I1, is in green.

Starting from the heel center and moving toward C1, a point located at a distance equal to the heel radius (HR) is defined as C3. A line is then drawn from C3, perpendicular to the longitudinal axis, to separate the heel from the middle portion of the foot. Two lines originating from points E2 and I2 and tangent to the heel circle are identified. The intersections of these tangents with the line separating the heel from the middle portion of the foot are assigned as points E3 and I3, respectively.

To evaluate segmentation accuracy, each ROI was manually adjusted after automatic processing, allowing direct comparison between predicted and reference regions. The Dice Similarity Coefficient was adopted as the primary metric for spatial overlap. It is calculated as:

$$DSC = (2 * |X \cap Y|) / (|X| + |Y|)$$

Where:

- $|X \cap Y|$ represents the number of pixels common to both sets X and Y .
- $|X|$ is the number of elements in the predicted set.
- $|Y|$ is the number of elements in the reference set.

The Dice coefficient was computed only for cases where an intersection existed (i.e., $Dice > 0$), to ensure meaningful comparisons. In addition to the mean Dice score per ROI type, the number of segmentation failures (i.e., ROIs with $Dice = 0$) is also reported.

III. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS

The image collection was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Plataforma Brasil. The first dataset by the CAAE: 78199123.0.0000.0099, under opinion number 6.734.473. The second dataset by the project CAAE: 79365217.9.0000.5547, under opinion number 2.493.904.

IV. RESULTS

The algorithm was integrated as an API into the Vizbox Thermal Analysis platform. The API receives a temperature matrix as input and returns segmented ROIs for further analysis and visualization. The interface allows users to view and refine the segmentation by moving, resizing or editing polygon vertices directly.

Fig. 6 Interface of the Vizbox Image Editor. The displayed ROIs correspond to the detection result without manual adjustment.

The top bar provides controls for adjusting temperature thresholds and selecting color palettes for better visualization. On the right panel, the interface displays parameters for each ROI along with a set of predefined thermal deltas between contralateral foot regions, with the option to define additional comparisons. When a ROI is selected, the tables are dynamically filtered to show only the relevant data.

Fig. 7 Interface of the Vizbodx Image Editor. The color palette was changed and a ROI is selected, filtering the data on the right panel. Vertex controls are displayed for the selected ROI.

A total of 92 thermal foot images were analyzed. Among these, 71 were successfully processed by the proposed segmentation tool, enabling the generation of all ROIs. As there are two feet per image, 142 ROIs were evaluated for each ROI type.

Table 1 summarizes the mean Dice scores for each anatomical ROI, considering only valid detections. Additionally, the number of failed (Dice = 0) and successful detections is reported.

Some recurrent segmentation errors occurred in test images where the foot temperature was close to ambient levels or where the absence of a physical background made it difficult to isolate the feet from the rest of the body. These conditions reduced thermal contrast and often caused ROI areas to be incorrectly extended into the background. Another common source of error was inaccurate localization of the foot bounding box, likely due to the limited size of the training dataset.

Table 1 Dice Similarity Coefficient by ROI type

Roi	Dice Coefficient	Dice = 0	Dice > 0
Anterior External	0,7711	3	139
Anterior Internal	0,7896	0	142
Middle External	0,8253	2	140
Middle Internal	0,7948	2	140
Heel	0,7581	2	140

V. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed tool demonstrated consistent performance in the automatic segmentation of predefined foot regions in thermal images. Dice coefficients exceeded 0.75 for all ROIs, showing strong agreement with manual annotations. In the worst-case category, only 3 out of 142 instances failed, with lower error counts in all other regions.

The automatic segmentation proved valuable in accelerating the manual adjustment process. Even when full accuracy was not achieved, it provided a reliable starting point, significantly reducing the time and effort required by the professional.

For future improvements, retraining the foot detection model with a larger and more diverse dataset could improve robustness with different anatomy and thermal conditions. Additionally, the integration of auxiliary correction methods may help address errors within the segmentation process and further enhance the quality of the result.

These findings support the potential of the proposed approach as a practical tool for thermal image analysis, particularly in clinical or screening settings where time efficiency and consistency are critical.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. A. Khandakar *et al.* (2022) Thermal Change Index-Based Diabetic Foot Thermogram Image Classification Using Machine Learning Techniques, *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 5, doi: 10.3390/s22051793.
2. S. S. Jeremiah, A. S. M. Moin, and A. E. Butler (2024) Virus-induced diabetes mellitus: revisiting infection etiology in light of SARS-CoV-2, *Metabolism*, vol. 156, p. 155917, doi: 10.1016/j.metabol.2024.155917.
3. N. A. Elsayed *et al.* (2023) 2. Classification and Diagnosis of Diabetes: Standards of Care in Diabetes—2023, *Diabetes Care*, vol. 46, pp. S19–S40, doi: 10.2337/dc23-S002.
4. R. Barbosa da Rocha *et al.* (2022) Fatores relacionados ao risco de feridas em pacientes com Diabetes mellitus Tipo 2, *Saúde e Pesquisa*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 1–12, doi: 10.17765/2176-9206.2022v15n3.e9838.
5. J. Muzy *et al.* (2021) Prevalência de diabetes mellitus e suas complicações e caracterização das lacunas na atenção à saúde a partir da triangulação de pesquisas, *Cad. Saúde Pública*, vol. 37, no. 5, doi: 10.1590/0102-311x00076120.
6. Y. K. Jan *et al.* (2024) Diagnosis, Pathophysiology and Management of Microvascular Dysfunction in Diabetes Mellitus, *Diagnostics*, vol. 14, no. 24, doi: 10.3390/diagnostics14242830.
7. I. Khosa *et al.* (2023) Automatic Diabetic Foot Ulcer Recognition Using Multi-Level Thermographic Image Data, *Diagnostics*, vol. 13, no. 16, doi: 10.3390/diagnostics13162637.
8. W. Wang *et al.* (2023) Prevalence and risk factors of diabetic peripheral neuropathy: A population- based cross- sectional

- study in China, *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*, vol. 39, no. 8, doi: 10.1002/dmrr.3702.
9. V. M. de L. Araujo *et al.* (2025) Prevalência de neuropatia diabética em indivíduos com diabetes mellitus e fatores de risco associados, *Caderno Pedagógico*, vol. 22, no. 2, p. e13440, doi: 10.54033/cadpedv22n2-019.
 10. O. J. M. do Nascimento, C. C. B. Pupe, and E. B. U. Cavalcanti (2016) Diabetic neuropathy, *Revista Dor*, vol. 17, doi: 10.5935/1806-0013.20160047.
 11. V. Panamonta *et al.* (2025) Plantar Thermogram Analysis Using Deep Learning for Diabetic Foot Risk Classification, *J Diabetes Sci Technol*, p. in press, doi: 10.1177/19322968251316563.
 12. G. Chemello, B. Salvatori, M. Morettini, and A. Tura (2022) Artificial Intelligence Methodologies Applied to Technologies for Screening, Diagnosis and Care of the Diabetic Foot: A Narrative Review, *Biosensors*, vol. 12, no. 11, doi: 10.3390/bios12110985.
 13. A. Khandakar *et al.* (2022) A Novel Machine Learning Approach for Severity Classification of Diabetic Foot Complications Using Thermogram Images, *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 11, doi: 10.3390/s22114249.
 14. P. R. J. Vas *et al.* (2018) The Diabetic Foot Attack: “’Tis Too Late to Retreat!”, *Int J Low Extrem Wounds*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 7–13, doi: 10.1177/1534734618755582.
 15. A. J. Boulton, L. Vileikyte, G. Ragnarson-Tennvall, and J. Apelqvist (2005) The global burden of diabetic foot disease, *Lancet*, vol. 366, no. 9498, pp. 1719–1724, doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(05)67698-2.
 16. H. Liew *et al.* (2024) Infrared Thermography Shows That a Temperature Difference of 2.2°C (4°F) or Greater Between Corresponding Sites of Neuropathic Feet Does Not Always Lead to a Diabetic Foot Ulcer, *J Diabetes Sci Technol*, doi: 10.1177/19322968241249970.
 17. Q. Qin *et al.* (2022) Factors Associated with the Local Increase of Skin Temperature, ‘Hotspot,’ of Callus in Diabetic Foot: A Cross-Sectional Study, *J Diabetes Sci Technol*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1174–1182, doi: 10.1177/19322968211011181.
 18. Q. Qin *et al.* (2022) Development of a self-monitoring tool for diabetic foot prevention using smartphone-based thermography: Plantar thermal pattern changes and usability in the home environment, *Drug Discov Ther*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 169–176, doi: 10.5582/ddt.2022.01050.
 19. H. J. Nam *et al.* (2024) The correlation between transcutaneous oxygen pressure (TcPO₂) and forward-looking infrared (FLIR) thermography in the evaluation of lower extremity perfusion according to angiosome, *Int Wound J*, vol. 21, no. 2, doi: 10.1111/iwj.14431.
 20. S. Muralidhara, A. Lucieri, A. Dengel, and S. Ahmed (2022) Holistic multi-class classification & grading of diabetic foot ulcerations from plantar thermal images using deep learning, *Health Inf Sci Syst*, vol. 10, no. 1, doi: 10.1007/s13755-022-00194-8.
 21. V. Srivastava *et al.* (2022) Effect of negative pressure wound therapy on wound thermometry in diabetic foot ulcers, *J Family Med Prim Care*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 7001–7007, doi: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_72_22.
 22. M. Aminuddin *et al.* (2025) Effectiveness of online education on thermography-based diabetic foot ulcer prevention for wound care specialists: a single-group quasi-experimental study, *Diabetol Int*, doi: 10.1007/s13340-025-00791-4.
 23. M. Faus Camarena *et al.* (2024) Update on the Use of Infrared Thermography in the Early Detection of Diabetic Foot Complications: A Bibliographic Review, *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 1, doi: 10.3390/s24010252.
 24. A. Bougrine *et al.* (2022) Segmentation of Plantar Foot Thermal Images Using Prior Information, *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 10, doi: 10.3390/s22103835.
 25. R. García-de-la-Peña *et al.* (2024) Use of Infrared Thermography in Podiatry: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis, *J. Clin. Med.*, vol. 13, no. 24, doi: 10.3390/jcm13247638.
 26. A. Ilo, P. Romsis, and J. Mäkelä (2020) Infrared Thermography and Vascular Disorders in Diabetic Feet, *J Diabetes Sci Technol*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 28–36, doi: 10.1177/1932296819871270.
 27. G. Piva *et al.* (2022) The Value of Infrared Thermography to Assess Foot and Limb Perfusion in Relation to Medical, Surgical, Exercise or Pharmacological Interventions in Peripheral Artery Disease: A Systematic Review, *Diagnostics*, vol. 12, no. 12, doi: 10.3390/diagnostics12123007.
 28. J. A. Keurhorst (2024) Enhancing Diabetic Foot Ulcer Risk Assessment in the VVT Sector: The Added Value of Thermal Imaging in Periodic Screening Master thesis, M.S. thesis.
 29. N. Arteaga-Marrero, A. Hernández-Guedes, J. Ortega-Rodríguez, and J. Ruiz-Alzola (2023) State-of-the-Art Features for Early-Stage Detection of Diabetic Foot Ulcers Based on Thermograms, *Biomedicines*, vol. 11, no. 12, doi: 10.3390/biomedicines11123209.
 30. O. Kurkela, J. Lahtela, M. Arffman, and L. Forma (2023) Infrared Thermography Compared to Standard Care in the Prevention and Care of Diabetic Foot: A Cost Analysis Utilizing Real-World Data and an Expert Panel, *Clinicoecon. Outcomes Res.*, vol. 15, pp. 111–123, doi: 10.2147/CEOR.S396137.
 31. Thermidas at: <https://thermidas.fi/solutions/telehealth>.
 32. ThermoHuman at: <https://thermohuman.com/2022/07/26/use-of-infrared-thermography-in-patients-with-plantar-fasciitis>.
 33. L. Requena-Bueno *et al.* (2020) Validation of ThermoHuman automatic thermographic software for assessing foot temperature before and after running, *J Therm Biol*, vol. 92, doi: 10.1016/j.jtherbio.2020.102639.
 34. C. M. L. S. Zolet (2020) O uso de imagens térmicas na avaliação do risco de complicações do pé diabético. M.S. thesis, Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica e de Computação.
 35. A. Hernandez-Guedes *et al.* (2023) Feature Ranking by Variational Dropout for Classification Using Thermograms from Diabetic Foot Ulcers, *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, doi: 10.3390/s23020757.

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